

PROCESSING OF A Ti-22Al-23Nb FOIL BY DIRECT HIP CONSOLIDATION OF POWDER

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ABSTRACT

A process which is aimed at reducing the cost of fabrication of foil product (0.125 mm thick) has been evaluated. The process involves the hot isostatic pressing (HIP) of metal powder without a binder in a sacrificial HIP can to produce a very thin (0.30 mm) as HIPed product, which is then cold rolled to final thickness. The evaluation has focused on producing orthorhombic titanium aluminide foils based on the Ti_2AlNb (orthorhombic) phase of the composition Ti-22Al-23Nb (at%). The main thrust of the study to date has been the evaluation of separation layers that inhibit the interaction of the powder with the HIP can.

INTRODUCTION

Ti- base metal matrix composites (MMCs) are of interest for high temperature applications where high specific strength and stiffness are required. Recent work [1] has shown that the Ti-22Al-23Nb/SCS-6 system shows promise. MMC fabrication can be accomplished using several methods. Powder techniques such as tape casting, plasma spray and powder cloth are typically used to produce composites that are made from difficult to work matrix alloys [2, 3]. These two powder processes rely on a fugitive binder to form the powder into the tape or cloth. This binder is typically organic, and thus can leave residual carbon after fabrication. Metal foils are fully dense and do not need a binder to retain their shape or architecture of the fibers. Metal foils also have the benefit of cold working, which helps to control microstructure and mechanical properties. Rolling also produces crystallographic texturing which can be used to enhance the directional properties of a composite [4].

Foil (0.125 mm thick) of moderate strength alloys with low work hardening rates is typically fabricated by a combination of hot and cold rolling. However, alloys with higher strength and higher work hardening rates are more difficult to roll, and other means of fabrication are used. Foils of high-strength alloys used to fabricate metal matrix composites are typically made by either plasma-spraying or conventional ingot metallurgy. In plasma spraying, pre-alloyed powder is sprayed into a sheet to a thickness of 0.250 mm thick, followed by rolling for final thickness and surface finish control. This method has the potential disadvantage of picking up oxygen and nitrogen during spraying. Conventional ingot metallurgy combines casting of the ingot followed by hot-working (forging and rolling), surface grinding, cold rolling and chemical milling to the final thickness [4]. The technique of hot-working followed by grinding and chemical milling has the disadvantage that there is up to an 80% material loss during these steps. Since the high-temperature alloys commonly use expensive raw materials, this is a costly and time consuming method of producing foil.

An innovative process has been developed for the production of metal foils which does not involve plasma spraying or ingot metallurgy. This process involves the HIPing of the metal powder in a sacrificial HIP can to form a sheet without the use of a fugative binder. This eliminates production losses associated with forming sheet from ingot, and it eliminates the contamination of the powder due to plasma spraying or use of a binder. This process does not impart much cold work into the powder product, which may make reduction of the segregation from solidification difficult. The microstructure of Ti-22Al-23Nb powder is comprised of a cellular structure of ordered β (B2) with intercellular α_2 of high aluminum composition [5]. The sluggish kinetics of the orthorhombic alloy requires a reduction in diffusion distances to totally eliminate this segregated microstructure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Foils approximately 0.25 mm thick have been made by direct HIP of powder. A schematic of the can designed to contain the powder is shown in **Figure 1**. The can consists of two cold-rolled steel sheets, 1.6 mm thick by 127 mm wide by 178 mm long. The sheets were formed at one end to accommodate a 6.4 mm O.D. steel tube, used to evacuate the HIP can. A separation layer was spot-welded continuously around the edges of each steel sheet, leaving a 1.6 mm gap near the edge of the steel. This separation layer was typically a 0.025 mm thick Mo, Ta or Nb foil, 114 mm wide by 152 mm long. The separation layer prevents interdiffusion of the powder alloy with the steel can. Other separation layers were evaluated including a braze stop-off that is composed of Y_2O_3 powder in an alcohol suspension and air plasma sprayed Al_2O_3 . Pre-oxidized MA956 foil (0.127 mm thick) was also evaluated as a potential separation layer.

Figure 1. Schematic of HIP can

Steel shim stock .38 mm thick and 12.7 mm wide was spot-welded onto the separation layer/steel sheet assembly to form a border around the two sides and bottom of one sheet. The two pieces of the HIP can were clamped together so that the shims and the separation layer were on the inside of the can. Two steel plates were clamped to the outside of the can to prevent warping during welding and pressure testing. The sides and bottom of the can were welded together in a vacuum. A 50.8 mm by 304.8 mm sheet of Mo foil was folded into a sleeve, 101.6

mm wide by 50.8 mm long, and taped to the top of the HIP can, such that 19.1 mm of the sleeve projected into the can. This sleeve was used to load the powder. The Mo foil sleeve was flared into a funnel, the can was placed upright in an ultrasonic cleaner and the powder was then loaded into the can. Vibration of the can by the ultrasonic cleaner during the powder loading resulted in a high density of packing of the powder particles. After loading the powder, the Mo sleeve was removed.

A steel shim 127 mm long by 0.38 mm thick was notched to accommodate the steel evacuation tube, and placed in the top of the HIP can. A piece of screen with a mesh size smaller than the powder size was spot-welded to one end of the steel tube. This prevented the powder from being sucked out of the can during evacuation. The screened end of the tube was inserted into the top of the HIP can, and the assembly was welded in a vacuum. The assembly was leak-tested and the retaining steel plates were removed. The can was heated under vacuum at 390-750°F (200-400°C); the steel tube was crimped off and welded shut to seal the contents at low internal pressure, and the can was ready for HIP. After the HIPing process has been completed, the powder foil was removed by either etching away the can, or the can was sectioned at the edges and separates due to the parting layer. HIPing conditions, particularly temperature, are selected based upon powder composition and size. The HIPing pressure is normally held constant at around 100 MPa, with HIPing times being nominally 3 hours, and pressure and temperature were increased simultaneously. For the Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, the HIP was performed at 100 - 138 MPa and 1150°C, as described in the results.

To determine the β transus temperature, powder from the same lot that was used to fabricate the powder foils, but of a coarser size, was HIPed in Ti-6Al-4V HIP cans at temperatures of 1050°C, 1075°C and 1100°C. In all instances the as HIPed microstructures indicated that the alloy was above the β transus temperature. A representative micrograph of material HIPed at 1075°C is shown in **Figure 2**. This result does not correspond with the powder foil HIP results where 1100°C produced a transformed β + retained α_2 microstructure. One explanation could be different oxygen contents due to different powder sizes [5].

Figure 2. Micrograph of structure obtained after the 1075°C HIP.

The powder size that was used in the initial portion of this study was -140 mesh (< 106 μm). In the latter stages of the study and for the β transus work, coarser powder was used in the evaluation of separation layers to conserve the -140 mesh powder for fabrication of foils that were to be cold rolled and tested for mechanical properties. Oxygen content of the powder as received was \approx 870 ppm.

RESULTS

Table 1 lists the powder foil experiments conducted to evaluate various separation layers.

Table 1. Experiments to evaluate separation layers for Ti-22Al-23Nb powder.

Can I.D.	Parting Layer	HIP Conditions	Comments
PF53	0.001" Mo foil	1100°C/3hr/104MPa	trans. $\beta + \alpha_2$; brittle - cracked when cut
PF54	0.001" Nb foil	1100°C/3hr/173MPa	trans. $\beta + \alpha_2$; brittle - cracked when cut
PF54A	0.001" Nb foil	1150°C/3hr/173MPa	transformed β , cold-rollable
PF60	0.001" Ta foil	1150°C/xhr/173MPa	HIP failed a few minutes into run; foil consolidated, rough surface
PF61	0.001" Ta foil	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	transformed β ; can be cut; did not cold-roll
PF62	0.001" Ta foil	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	HIPed at IMT for comparison with PF61, no warpage
PF63	PSed alumina one side only	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	HIPed at IMT, APS Al_2O_3 side separated after sectioning
PF64	Y_2O_3 Stop-off	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	Can was warped, powder foil did not separate from can and was brittle
PF65	Y_2O_3 Stop-off	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	Double thick Y_2O_3 , can did part, powder foil was still brittle
PF66	Nb-Foil/Ti-24-11 Powder	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	In-situ formation of ortho, could be cut.
PF67	Pre-oxidized MA956 foil	1150°C/3hr/138MPa	One side of can separated, powder foil was brittle

The initial trials, PF53 through PF62, attempted to reproduce the results from work done on Ti-6242, Ti-24Al-11Nb and superalloy powder foils that utilized single refractory element foils as separation layers. These refractory element foils were reactive with the Ti-22Al-23Nb powder and at 1150°C created a stable β microstructure that was not brittle, but was not desirable for MMC fabrication. The next trials used an oxide layer to try to inhibit the reaction of the powder and the HIP can during HIPing, as detailed below. PF66 relied on the formation of the orthorhombic aluminide phase through the in-situ reaction of Ti-24Al-11Nb (at%) with the Nb separation foil.

The powder foils were generally 102 mm by 102 mm and 0.25-0.30 mm thick, when made using 0.38 mm shim stock in the HIP can. The thickness variation around the foil was usually ± 0.05 mm. The 0.38 mm shims may represent the practical limit of this technique, since it was very difficult to load powder evenly into the can with this a smaller gap. Shims 0.25 mm thick were used with superalloy powder, and uniform loading was not achieved.

PF53: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Mo foil separation layer, HIPed at 1100°C/3hr/104MPa. The Mo foil separation layer produced the microstructure shown in **Figure 3**. The Mo foil reacted with the Ti-22Al-23Nb powder to produce a two-phase microstructure of blocky retained α_2 and transformed β . This material was brittle as-HIPed and cracked when samples were cut off of the foil. Samples of the foil were heat treated at 1150°C for 4 hours in argon, and the resulting microstructure was β with blocky retained α_2 . Samples were also heat treated at 1200°C for 4 hour in argon, and the resultant microstructure produced was β with on-cooling α_2 or orthorhombic phase precipitated near the center, but not near the edges where the Mo foil reacted with the powder. This microstructure was not the desired for composite mechanical properties, so the Mo foil approach was not evaluated any further.

Figure 3. Microstructure of Ti 22Al-23Nb Powder Foil with Mo Foil Separation Layer.

PF54: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Nb foil separation layer, HIPed at 1100°C/3hr/104MPa. Nb foil was next evaluated as a separation layer, and the HIP temperature remained at 1100°C. The as HIPed microstructure was again blocky retained α_2 and transformed β , similar to the Mo foil results. Therefore, no further work was conducted on the material HIPed at this temperature.

PF54A: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Nb foil separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/104MPa. The HIP temperature was increased by 50°C to be above the β transus in hopes that the microstructure would be single phase β at the HIPing temperature and transform to orthorhombic on cooling, as seen in **Figure 4**. The Nb foil is retained on the surface of the powder foil, and the reaction layer is limited to the first 50 μm . In the reaction layer there is a third phase which is blocky and appears at the line between the Nb foil and the powder foil. No analysis was conducted to identify this phase. The as HIPed powder foil was cold rolled to a reduction of 19 - 35%, depending on the initial thickness and the material did not crack at this percentage of cold work.

Figure 4. Microstructure of Ti -22Al-23Nb Powder Foil with Nb Foil Separation Layer.

PF60: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Ta foil separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/xhr/173MPa. The HIP run failed several minutes into the experiment. The resultant powder foil had a rough surface although the foil was almost completely consolidated. No further work was performed.

PF61: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Ta foil separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. The microstructure of this powder foil product consisted of transformed β , which is similar to PF54A. The HIP can from this run was badly warped and no viable explanation could be found.

PF62: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Ta foil separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. This experiment was a duplicate of PF61 processed at a different facility and was intended to determine if the warpage of the HIP cans was due to the facility where the HIPing occurred. The microstructure of the product was the same as PF61, therefore, no more work was performed.

PF63: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, plasma sprayed Al_2O_3 separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. This experiment was conducted to determine if dense air plasma sprayed (APS) alumina was stable with the Ti-22Al-23Nb powder at the HIP temperatures. The microstructure indicated that Al_2O_3 had spalled off of the Al_2O_3 separation layer and had sintered into the powder foil. This result indicated that APS Al_2O_3 would not provide an effective separation layer.

PF64: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Y_2O_3 stop-off separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. The Y_2O_3 stop-off was painted on in only one application, and did not eliminate the reaction of the powder with the can. The can was warped after HIPing and the powder foil product was brittle and cracked when pried away from the can. The powder foil also appears to have not consolidated completely. This combination was repeated for PF65.

PF65: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, Y_2O_3 stop-off separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. This experiment duplicated PF64, but for this experiment the Y_2O_3 stop-off was painted on in many layers so that it was thicker than in PF64. As a result, the powder foil completely separated from the can after the edges were cut away, but the powder foil still brittle. As seen in **Figure 5**, this powder foil also has surfaces that appear to have retained the shape of the input powder. Notice also the light grey material that is between the undulations in the surface. Electron microprobe analysis (EMPA) indicates that this material is Y_2O_3 that apparently sintered into the valleys of the powder during HIPing and forced the powder to retain its shape at the surface after HIPing. The dark phase shown in **Figure 5** has the α_2 composition, and the matrix has the orthorhombic composition. This foil was brittle so there was no further analysis.

Figure 5. Microstructure of Powder Foil with Y_2O_3 Stop-off Separation Layer.

PF66: Ti-24Al-11Nb powder, Nb foil separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. The idea behind this experiment was to produce the orthorhombic composition and microstructure desired in-situ. By using the Nb foil as both a separation layer and an alloying element, it was thought that the issue of reactivity with the separation layer could be overcome. As seen in **Figure 6**, which is a backscattered electron image, three distinct layers formed during HIPing. An EMPA line traverse stepped every 5µm showed that the layer nearest the surface is pure Nb, the next is around the Ti-22Al-23Nb composition and the composition of the innermost layer is a mix of Ti-24Al-11Nb and Ti-22Al-23Nb. This indicates it is possible to produce the orthorhombic composition in-situ during HIP. This is area for further study.

Figure 6. Microstructure of Ti-24Al-11Nb Powder and a Nb Foil Separation Layer.

PF67: Ti-22Al-23Nb powder, pre-oxidized MA956 separation layer, HIPed at 1150°C/3hr/138MPa. This arrangement allowed the can to separate, but the powder foil was stuck to one side and was brittle when separated from the can. EMPA indicated that the Fe from the MA956 diffused into the powder foil to a depth of $\approx 160\mu\text{m}$ and created what appears to be a stable β microstructure to that depth. This region was brittle, as evidenced by the cracks that propagated through the thickness of this region and were stopped by the Ti-22Al-23Nb powder foil. Because of the foil brittleness, no further work was done. The MA956 remained attached to the powder foil in most areas.

DISCUSSION

The success of the powder foil technique in fabricating cold-rollable foils from Ti-6242, Ti-24Al-21Nb and various Ni-base superalloys were encouraging enough to apply this method to making Ti-22Al-23Nb foils as the initial part of a study on foil and MMC properties. The planned work included microstructural characterization and mechanical property evaluation of the foils, and of neat (fiberless) panels consolidated from the foils. Of interest were the phase types and distribution, elemental segregation potentially arising from segregation in the powder particles themselves, and grain size, as well as the effects on these microstructural parameters on the tensile strength and elongation of foil and HIPed panels. In addition, after cold-rolling trials of the powder foils were conducted and optimum rolling conditions determined, it was planned to use the rolled foils to fabricate Ti-22Al-23Nb/SCS-6 SiC MMC's, and to evaluate microstructure and properties of these composites. As seen in the current study, this alloy composition was fabricable into foils using the powder technique, and the foils were cold-rollable when the correct foil fabrication conditions, e.g., HIP parameters and parting layers,

were chosen. The difficulties in determining the appropriate parting layer for use with this high-temperature alloy have resulted in some redirection of the effort, and have delayed property evaluation of foils, neat product and composite.

However, the results from several of the powder foil runs show promise. These include the runs made from Ti-22Al-23Nb powder and either Nb or Ta foils. Further work on these foils will include cold pack-rolling with intermediate stress relief anneals to look at microstructure and texture development in this processing. Evaluation of the best methods for removing the refractory metal foils from the surface of the powder foils also needed, unless they can be incorporated into the MMC's with beneficial effects.

In addition, the powder foil made from Ti-24Al-11Nb with a Nb foil parting layer was interesting from a microstructural point of view, and is potentially cold-rollable. There will be combinations of cold-rolling and heat-treating conducted to determine if the foil can be cold-worked and if the deformation enhances homogenization of the foil during heat treatment.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The fabrication of thin (~0.38 mm) foils by direct HIP of powder has been demonstrated for the Ti-22Al-23Nb composition. The method of fabrication uses a specially designed HIP can.
2. The reactivity of the Ti-22Al-23Nb composition coupled with the high HIPing temperatures eliminate many conventional separation layers including Mo and Ta foil and Y₂O₃ stop-off.
3. Ti-22Al-23Nb powder HIPed with a Nb separation layer is ductile and can be cold rolled to reductions between 19 and 35%.
4. Production of the orthorhombic composition via an in-situ reaction of Nb foil and Ti-24Al-11Nb powder has been demonstrated.

REFERENCES

1. P.R. Smith, J.A. Graves, C.G. Rhodes, Preliminary Mechanical Property Assessment of a SiC/Orthorhombic Titanium Aluminide Composite. Structural Intermetallics, R. Darolia et. al. editors, *TMS*, 765 - 771 (1992).
2. R.A. MacKay, S.L. Draper, A.M. Ritter, P.A. Siemers, A Comparison of the Mechanical Properties and Microstructures of Intermetallic Matrix Composites Fabricated by Two Different Methods. *Met Trans A*, 25A, 1443 - 1455 (1994).
3. C.T. Lynch, J.P. Kershaw, Metal Matrix Composites. CRC Press, Cromwood Parkway, Cleveland, Ohio 44128. pps. 15 - 25.
4. I.M. Sukonnik, P.R. Smith, J.A. Graves, C.G. Rhodes, M.C. Shaw, S. Krishnamurthym A. Pandey, Advances in Thermomechanical Processing of Titanium Aluminide Orthorhombic Foils. *Proceedings from TMC Workshop, Orlando FL, 6 -8 Nov, 98 - 114* (1991).
5. C.G. Rhodes, J.A. Graves, P.R. Smith, M.R. James, Characterization of orthorhombic Titanium Aluminide Alloys. Structural Intermetallics, R. Darolia et al. editors, *TMS*, 42 - 52 (1992).